

THE EFFECT OF FABRIC SCOURING ON FIRE AND MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF FLAME RETARDED FLAX/PP AND FLAX/PLA COMPOSITES

W. Pornwannachai¹, G. Smart¹, M.H. Akonda² and B.K. Kandola^{1*}

¹ Institute for Materials Research and Innovation, University of Bolton, Bolton, BL3 5AB, UK

² Tilsatec Advanced Materials, Tilsatec Ltd., Wakefield, UK

* Corresponding author (b.kandola@bolton.ac.uk)

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1 Introduction

Natural fibre composites are becoming popular in automotive industry due to their biodegradability, renewability, and hence more environmental friendly properties [1-5]. However, natural fibres have low fire resistance, which has restricted their growth in applications where the fire regulations are stringent. Therefore, flame retardant (FR) treatments are required to improve their fire resistance. The common method of application of flame retardants to fabrics is to pad-dry and/or cure. Fabrics containing natural fibres, in particular cellulose are usually scoured prior to any finish. This increases fabric wettability and hence pickup of the finish. Scouring usually removes sizing, hemicelluloses, lignin, pectin, waxes etc from cellulosic fibres. In composites, however the presence of lignin, pectin etc could be advantageous as they are reported to have better thermal stabilities than cellulosic structures [4,5]. However, not much is known about the effect of scouring on physical, mechanical and flammability properties of the composites. The aim of this work is to study the effect of scouring on the FR uptake levels of flax/PP and flax/PLA woven fabric, and fire and mechanical performance of composites prepared from these fabrics.

For textile related applications flax fibres are usually scoured with sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium bi-carbonate (Na₂CO₃) or a detergent (sodium phosphate, Na₃PO₄) solutions prior to other treatments in order to remove the impurity present

in the fibres, hence also resulting in improvement in the absorption of fibres for dyes and other finishes [6]. There is however, no literature available on the use/effect of these scouring agents on properties of hybrid fabrics such as flax/polypropylene (PP) or flax/poly(lactic acid) (PLA). To study the effect of different scouring agents on hybrid fabrics, these scouring agents have been used at different concentrations. Mono-ammonium phosphate (AP), one of the commonly used flame retardants (FR) for cellulosic materials, has been chosen as a flame retardant for this study. The optimized scouring conditions for maximum FR pickup and minimum fibre mass loss were chosen to scour fabrics, which were then melt pressed to produce composite laminates.

2 Experiments

2.1 Materials

Flax, flax/PP and flax/PLA woven fabrics (50/50 wt-%) were supplied by Composites Evolution (UK). These woven fabrics were of 4x4 hopsack structure with areal densities as follows: flax = 467 g/m², flax/PP = 465 g/m² and flax/PLA = 493 g/m². Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), and sodium phosphate (Na₃PO₄) were used to prepare scouring solutions of different concentrations, given in Table 1. Mono-ammonium phosphate (AP) was used as 20 wt-% solution to treat fabrics.

2.2 Fabric scouring and FR treatment

Flax/PP and flax/PLA were scoured using different chemicals and varied conditions as shown in Table 1. The scoured fabrics were subsequently neutralised with 0.5 wt-% acetic acid solution, followed by rinsing with water before drying in an oven at 80 °C for 1 hr. Based on the results discussed in a later section, 10 g/L of Na₂CO₃ solution and 10 g/L of Na₃PO₄ were selected to optimize scouring time by scouring the fabrics with these chemicals at 60 °C for different times. The scoured and non-scoured fabrics were then treated with mono-ammonium phosphate (AP) solution by padding followed by drying in an oven at 100 °C for 5 min.

The percent weight loss and FR uptake of the fabric samples were recorded by weighing the fabrics before/after scouring process and FR treatment with AP solution, respectively. This information was used to identify the best scouring solution and scouring time that causes minimal fibre weight loss with significantly improved FR uptake.

2.3 Composite preparation and characterisation

An assembly of eight layers of each type of control and flame retarded samples from non-scoured and scoured fabrics was pressed at 190 °C for 3.5 min under 50 kg/cm² pressure to obtain laminates of ~3 mm thicknesses.

The fire performance of the composite laminates was evaluated using UL-94 and cone calorimetry. The UL-94 test was conducted in both horizontal and vertical orientations, from which rate of burning for each sample was also recorded. For cone calorimetry, three specimens of each sample were tested at 35 kW/m² according to ISO 5660.

The mechanical performance of composites was evaluated in tensile, flexural and impact modes. Tensile and flexural tests were conducted using an Instron 3369. Tensile test was performed using 50 kN load cell with the crosshead speed at 1 mm/min. The gauge length of each specimen was 100 mm.

Polymeric tabs were bonded at the end of specimens to improve the gripping and to ensure failure within the gauge region. In flexural mode three point bending tests were carried out using a 100 N load cell at 0.5 mm/min crosshead speed. Impact properties of composites were tested using an Instron Dynatub with 1.02 kg load and 100 mm falling height.

2.4 Fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion

The morphology of the fractured surfaces of composite laminates after tensile test was studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Hitachi S-3400N) with the acceleration voltage 10 kV. The samples were gold coated using Polaron Range SC7620 Sputter Coater with 60 s plasma exposition prior to analysis.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Selection of suitable scouring solution for fabrics

In order to study the effect of different alkaline solutions on the FR uptake of fabrics, scouring/washing process was carried out according to standard procedure used for flax fabrics as discussed in Section 2.2. The fabric samples were weighed before and after the process and the change in weight of the fabrics after treatments is given in Table 1. The results show that 20 g/L NaOH is the most aggressive solution for scouring flax fabric as the percent weight loss is very high (16.2%) compared to other solutions (~10%). For flax/PLA a significant weight loss of 39.2% is observed after scoured with NaOH, which could be due to PLA dissolving in a strong alkaline solution. The ester group (-COO-) of PLA, similar to other aliphatic polyester can hydrolyse with an alkali solution through saponification reaction [7]. However, with Na₂CO₃ and Na₃PO₄ (weaker alkali agents) solutions the weight loss is less than in NaOH. For flax/PP fabrics the effect of alkali solutions on weight loss is less compared to flax fabrics and

flax/PLA, which is as expected due to alkali resistance of PP.

As can be seen from the results in Table 1, with all scouring agents used the weight loss of all fabrics and in particular flax/PLA is more than expected if only sizing was removed. This could be due to lignin and pectin also being removed during the process. However, for composites these components are useful and only size needs to be removed. Therefore, scouring/washing conditions needs to be optimised in order to identify the minimum weight loss that significantly improves FR uptake. Based on this criteria, Na_2CO_3 and Na_3PO_4 were selected for further study.

To optimize the scouring conditions, FR uptake values of flax, flax/PP and flax/PLA fabric after scouring at 60 °C with Na_2CO_3 (10 g/L solution) and Na_3PO_4 (10 g/L solution) for different times were measured and are shown in Figure 1. Non-scoured flax fabric, as expected, showed better FR pick-up (85%) compared to non-scoured flax/PP (70%) and flax/PLA (75%) fabrics. On flax fabrics both Na_2CO_3 and Na_3PO_4 showed a very little effect of scouring up to 20 min. The FR uptake increased after 30 min, reaching a maximum of 90% after 60 min scouring. For flax/PP fabric, Na_2CO_3 increased the FR uptake from 70% to 87% in 30 min, which then remained stable up to 90 min. Similar trend was shown by Na_3PO_4 . For flax/PLA, Na_2CO_3 significantly increased the FR uptake from 75% to 84% after 45 min, while Na_3PO_4 increased the FR uptake to same level after 60 min. Based on these results, Na_2CO_3 (10 g/L solution) with 30 minutes scouring time was selected as an optimized condition to treat the fabrics prior to treatment with the flame retardant.

3.2 Fire performance of composite laminates

The fire performance of laminates prepared from non-scoured/scoured control and AP flame retarded flax/PP and flax/PLA fabrics was evaluated by UL-94 and cone calorimetric tests.

3.2.1 Effect of flame retardant

According to UL-94 standard test, the laminates were tested in both vertical and horizontal orientation and the results are given in Table 3. The control flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates failed vertical rating as the specimens were completely burnt up to the sample holder. The treatment of flax/PP with AP did not improve the UL-94 rating of the AP-Flax/PP laminate, as the sample burned completely. However, AP significantly improved fire performance of flax/PLA and the laminate passed UL-94 vertical test with V-0 rating. The burning rate of samples in vertical and horizontal orientation were also measured in order to have better understanding of the effect of AP on flammability of composite laminates, Table 3. The burning rate of flax/PP laminate was 166 mm/min in vertical and 21 mm/min in horizontal test. Whereas, flax/PLA laminate had vertical burning rate 135 mm/min and horizontal burning rate 12 mm/min, i.e., less than flax/PP. The addition of AP in composites significantly reduced vertical and horizontal burning rate of flax/PP and flax/PLA laminate as shown in Table 3. With the addition of AP in flax/PP laminate, vertical burning rate was reduced to 65 mm/min (about 60% reduction), and horizontal burning rate could not be calculated as the flame went out soon after removal of the burner. For AP containing flax/PLA laminate, vertical and horizontal burning rate could not be calculated as the samples did not ignite, resulting in V-0 rating.

The flammability results of the laminate samples evaluated by cone calorimetry in terms of time-to-ignition (TTI), flame-out time, peak of heat release rate (PHRR), time to peak of heat release rate (tPHRR), total heat released (THR) and effective heat of combustion (EHC) are presented in Table 4. The graphical presentation of heat release rate as a function of time can be seen in Figures 2. Flax/PP laminate ignited at 28 s and showed two peaks of heat release rate (PHRR) of 429 and 372 kW/m² intensity at 73 s and 163 s, respectively, producing

89 MJ/m² of THR. Flax/PLA laminate however, ignited at 45 s (17 s later than flax/PP), also showed two peaks of heat release, 266 kW/m² at 69 s and 287 kW/m² at 142 s, which are much lower than those of flax/PP. The THR of flax/PLA (48 MJ/m²) is also much lower than that of flax/PP. These double peaked heat release rate behaviour of flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates is a typical behaviour of a cellulosic fibre - composite. The first peak of heat release rate represents the burning of laminate after ignition. During this stage the flax fibres start charring. This charred layer could act as thermal barrier for the underlying polymer, slowing down its burning until the charred layer cracks and then the second peak appears [8]. The addition of mono-ammonium phosphate in flax/PP laminate (11.3 wt-% for AP treated flax/PP fabric, Table 2) did not affect time-to-ignition of the laminate (AP Flax/PP), but prolonged flame out time from 344 s of control sample to 517 s, however, both PHRR values were significantly reduced. The first PHRR was reduced from 429 kW/m² of control sample to 255 kW/m² in AP-Flax/PP, indicating effectiveness of AP in reducing flammability. The second PHRR, which represents the effectiveness of char formed as a result of condensed phase activity of AP was also decreased from 372 kW/m² in control (flax/PP) to 199 kW/m² in AP Flax/PP. THR (81 MJ/m²) and EHC (25 MJ/kg) of AP flax/PP laminate were also reduced compared to the control sample (89 MJ/m² THR and 28 MJ/kg EHC). AP generally works in condensed phase by promoting more char formation, which can act as a thermal barrier to inhibit further decomposition of the underlying polymer [9]. When AP is heated it will release phosphoric acid which then will react with hydroxyl groups in cellulosic materials to form phosphorus ester that can catalyse the dehydration of cellulose leading to promoting char during combustion [9-12]. The acid may also cross-link with cellulose leading to change of pyrolysis pathway to yield less flammable decomposed products [12]. This condensed phase effect of AP is also supported by an improvement in

char formation of the sample percent char yield was also increased from 4.3% to 13.3%.

AP showed better efficiency in flame retarding flax/PLA laminate compared to flax/PP, as can be seen from results in Table 4. With the presence of AP, TTI of AP Flax/PLA laminate was delayed from 45 to 62 s, and the flame out time was also shortened to 81 s. Moreover, presence of AP significantly decreased PHRR, THR and EHC of the AP Flax/PLA laminate. THR was reduced to 14 MJ/m² (69% reduction) and THR was reduced to 4 MJ/kg (71% reduction). Both peak heat release values were also significantly reduced, the first PHRR to 51 kW/m² and the second to 58 kW/m², showing about 80% reduction of each peak compared to the control sample. The condensed phase activity of AP also improved the % char yield from 4.1% in control flax/PLA to 14.2% in AP Flax/PLA. Time to second PHRR was also increased from 142s in control sample to 299 s in AP- Flax/PLA.

3.2.2 Effect of scouring

According to UL-94 results in Table 3, the scouring process had a negative effect on flammability of non flame retarded flax/PP and flax/PLA laminate as the burning rates in both vertical and horizontal orientation are slightly higher than respective control samples. The results though are within the experimental error range (Table 3). This is possibly due to the loss of lignin and pectin during scouring process, which have better thermal stability than cellulosic structure [4,5]. However, comparing the flammability of flame retarded composite laminates between scoured and non-scoured samples, the scouring process (pre-treatment of fabric) showed minimal effect. For example, the vertical burning rate of AP-Flax/PP and S-AP Flax/PP is 65 and 63 mm/min, respectively. This might be due to the higher FR uptake by scoured fabric (see Table 2) resulting in higher FR concentration in composite laminate produced from scoured fabric compared to those of non-scoured samples.

On comparing the results of non flame retarded laminate from scoured and non-scoured fabric shown in Table 4, it can be seen that the scouring process slightly increased flammability of flax/PP and flax/PLA laminate due to the removal of lignin and pectin during the scouring process. THR_s increased from 89 MJ/m² in flax/PP to 92 MJ/m² in S-Flax/PP, and 48 MJ/m² in flax/PLA to 54 MJ/m² in S-Flax/PLA. Both PHRR values for both samples are also slightly higher than the respective control samples. As can be seen from Table 2, scouring helped in increasing the FR uptake of both flax/PP and flax/PLA fabrics, hence the AP concentration in S-AP Flax/PP and S-AP Flax/PLA laminates is higher than respective samples from non-scoured fabrics. Laminates with scoured fabrics are expected to show better flame retardant properties as compared to non-scoured ones. However, as seen from results in Table 4, this is not the case. Scouring reduced TTI; increased PHRRs, THR and EHC of FR treated flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates. This reduction could be due to removal of hemicelluloses, lignin and pectin from flax fibres during scouring process [5], decreasing the overall cellulosic content of flax.

In summary, both UL-94 and cone calorimetric results have shown that scouring of hybrid fabrics prior to flame retardant treatment has a negative effect on flammability of flame retarded flax/PP and flax/PLA composite laminates

3.3 Mechanical performance

The mechanical test results of the control and flame retardant composite laminates from scoured and non-scoured fabrics tested in tensile, flexural and impact mode are given in Table 5. The tensile modulus of tested specimens was calculated from the elastic region of stress-strain curves.

3.3.1 Effect of flame retardant

The tensile moduli of control flax/PP and flax/PLA laminate were 6.6 GPa and 10.2 GPa, respectively. The presence of AP flame retardant reduced the

tensile modulus of the flax/PP laminates from 6.6 GPa to 5.7 GPa in AP Flax/PP. However, the tensile modulus of flax/PLA was significantly reduced with the addition of AP, i.e., >50% reduction was observed. The tensile properties of composite laminates are reinforcement dependent [13]. Lower modulus of flax/PP indicates poor fibre-matrix adhesion. The reduction of tensile modulus in AP treated laminates is due to the fact that during laminate preparation, mono-ammonium phosphate could start decomposing (decomposition temperature = 170 – 180 °C) producing phosphoric acid, which reacts with the cellulosic flax fibre, reducing the fibre strength. The effect is more pronounced in flax/PLA because phosphoric acid also reacts with PLA, reducing the strength even more.

The flexural modulus of flax/PP laminate was 8.2 GPa while flax/PLA laminate was 16.5 GPa (see Table 5). The presence of AP in flax/PP laminates slightly improved the flexural modulus from 8.2 GPa of control flax/PP laminate to 8.4 GPa. On the other hand, AP significantly reduced flexural modulus of flax/PLA laminate from 16.5 GPa of control sample to 4.7 GPa of AP Flax/PLA. As the flexural properties of composite laminates are polymer matrix dependent rather than fibre reinforcement [13], AP has less effect on PP containing sample compared to PLA containing sample. PP, being non-polar, does not react with AP, whereas ester group of PLA polymer has reacted with phosphoric acid generated from AP flame retardant.

The laminates were also tested for their impact resistance. From Table 5, impact moduli of flax/PP and flax/PLA laminate were 11.0 GPa and 14.9 GPa, respectively. The presence of AP in laminates decreased the impact moduli of both flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates. While the reduction in impact modulus of AP Flax/PP was from 11.0 GPa of control sample to 9.4 GPa, in case of flax/PLA the reduction was ~90%, from 14.9 GPa of control

laminate to 1.6 GPa in AP Flax/PLA. Similar to flexural properties, impact properties are also matrix dependent [13]. Since AP reacts with PLA, PLA's mechanical properties are significantly reduced.

3.3.2 Effect of scouring

The scouring of flax/PP and flax/PLA slightly increased the tensile moduli of the laminates prepared from these fabrics compared to those from non-scoured fabrics. The tensile modulus of flax/PP was increased from 6.6 GPa to 8.4 GPa for S-Flax/PP (27% increase), while for flax/PLA laminate, the value increased from 10.2 GPa to 10.9 GPa in S-Flax/PLA (7% increase). This increase of tensile modulus may be due to removal of sizing, hemicelluloses, lignin, pectin, waxes etc. in flax fibre during scouring process, leading to change in fine structure of cellulose and production of rough surface [2]. This physically improves interfacial bonding between fibre and matrix by giving rise to additional sites for mechanical interlocking, therefore promoting more polymer penetration at the interface [14-16]. The fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion plays an important role in mechanical performance of composites. The greater fibre-matrix adhesion gives better load-transfer between fibre reinforcement and polymer matrix resulting in greater mechanical performance [14-16]. Similar results were observed for flame retarded laminates, where scouring increased the tensile modulus. To study the effect of scouring on the fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to observe the fibre-matrix adhesion from the fracture surface of composites samples after tensile tests. As seen in Figure 3, the laminate from scoured fabric shows better fibre-matrix adhesion compared to laminate from non-scoured fabric. Figure 3(a) shows that the fibre breaking position in laminate from scoured fabric is at similar level as the fracture surface of polymer matrix, which indicates a good adhesion between fibre and matrix [17,18]. Whereas, Figure 3(b) for

non-scoured sample shows that the fibres have been pulled-out before breaking from the matrix, long fibres protruding through the fractured surface can be clearly seen. This shows that the scouring improved the fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion of composites resulting in improvement of mechanical properties as shown by increase of tensile modulus.

The effect of scouring on flexural properties is also similar to tensile properties as can be seen from Table 5. With scouring flexural modulus of non-FR treated flax/PP increased from 8.2 GPa in control sample to 10.9 GPa in S-Flax/PP (33% increase), while for non-FR treated flax/PLA it increased from 16.2 GPa to 18.5 GPa (14% increase). This increase in flexural modulus represents increased fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion in composite leading to better load-transfer between fibre reinforcement and the polymer matrix [14-16]. However, this effect is more pronounced in flax/PP laminate than in flax/PLA. The scouring caused some hydrolysis of PLA, hence the improvement in mechanical properties of flax/PLA is less. For AP containing flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates, the flexural moduli of laminate from scoured fabrics were also higher than those from non-scoured fabrics. The modulus of AP flax/PP laminate increased from 8.4 GPa to 8.8 GPa for S-AP Flax/PP, while the modulus of AP flax/PLA laminate increased from 4.7 GPa to 5.3 GPa in S-AP Flax/PLA.

The effect of scouring on impact modulus is similar to that on flexural. The control and flame retarded laminates from scoured fabrics showed slightly higher impact modulus than non-scoured samples.

4 Conclusions

Mono-ammonium phosphate significantly improved the fire retardancy of flax/PP and flax/PLA laminates. While AP containing flax/PP failed UL-94 test, the burning rate was reduced more than 50% in vertical orientation. In horizontal direction the sample self extinguished. AP showed even

better flame retardant efficiency with flax/PLA laminate as the sample did not ignite, resulting in achieving V-0 rating. Cone calorimetric results also confirmed the efficiency of AP with reduction of PHRRs, THR, EHC and enhancement in residual char formation in flame retarded samples. The presence of AP however reduced mechanical properties of laminates, the effect was very pronounced in flax/PLA.

The scouring process (pre-treatment of fabric prior to further processing) slightly increased flammability of laminates, shown by increased PHRRs, THR and EHC from cone calorimetric results in all samples, which could be explained due to removal of hemicelluloses, lignin and pectin, which have higher thermal stability than cellulosic structure. However, scouring helped in increasing the mechanical properties, which can be explained due to change in the fine structure of cellulose, producing rough surface leading to interfacial bonding improvement by increasing additional sites of mechanical interlocking between fibre and matrix. The increase in mechanical properties with scouring process though is minimal. Since with scouring, the flame retardancy of the laminates is reduced and the enhancement in mechanical properties is also marginal, it can be concluded that there is no advantage of using an extra process of scouring during flame retardant composite laminate preparation.

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Table 1. Weight loss of flax, flax/PP and flax/PLA fabrics after scouring

Sample	Scouring agent	Conc. (g/L)	Temp (°C)	Time (hrs)	Weight loss (%)
Flax	NaOH	20	90 ± 5	1	16.2
	Na ₂ CO ₃	10	70 ± 5	1	10.4
		10	70 ± 5	2	11.9
	Na ₃ PO ₄	10	50 ± 5	1	10.1
5		40 ± 5	1	6.6	
Flax/PP	NaOH	20	90 ± 5	1	11.1
	Na ₂ CO ₃	10	70 ± 5	1	7.5
		10	70 ± 5	2	7.7
	Na ₃ PO ₄	10	50 ± 5	1	7.0
Flax/PLA	NaOH	20	90 ± 5	1	39.2
	Na ₂ CO ₃	10	70 ± 5	1	8.8
		10	70 ± 5	2	10.9
	Na ₃ PO ₄	10	50 ± 5	1	5.5

Table 2. Weight loss and percent FR content of flax/PP and flax/PLA fabric after scouring with Na₂CO₃ (10 g/L solution) and FR treatment with 20 wt-% AP solution

Sample	Weight loss of fabric after scouring (%)	FR content in the fabrics (%)
S-Flax/PP	2.3 ± 0.2	-
AP Flax/PP	-	11.3 ± 2.4
S-AP Flax/PP	2.2 ± 0.1	15.3 ± 0.2
S-Flax/PLA	4.5 ± 0.7	-
AP Flax/PLA	-	12.3 ± 0.7
S-AP Flax/PLA	4.4 ± 0.4	14.6 ± 0.3

Fig. 1 FR uptake of flax, flax/PP and flax/PLA fabrics after scouring with; a) Na₂CO₃ (10 g/L solution), b) Na₃PO₄ (10 g/L solution) for different times.

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Fig. 2 Heat release rate curve of control and FR flax/PP (a) and flax/PLA (b) composites from scoured and non-scoured fabric

Fig. 3 The SEM images of fracture surface of AP treated flax/PP laminates from scoured (a) and non-scoured (b) fabrics

Table 3. UL-94 results of control and FR flax/PP and flax/PLA composites from scoured and non-scoured fabric (vertical and horizontal)

Sample	UL-94						
	Horizontal flame spread			Vertical flame spread			V-rate
	B. Length (mm)	B. Time (s)	B. Rate (mm/min)	B. Length (mm)	B. Time (s)	B. Rate (mm/min)	
Flax/PP	100	295 ± 32	21 ± 2	100	36 ± 2	166 ± 8	Failed
S-Flax/PP	100	277 ± 6	22 ± 1	100	36 ± 5	171 ± 24	Failed
AP Flax/PP ¹	-	-	-	100	93 ± 4	65 ± 3	Failed
S-AP Flax/PP ¹	-	-	-	100	96 ± 0	63 ± 0	Failed
Flax/PLA	100	497 ± 21	12 ± 1	100	45 ± 3	135 ± 7	Failed
S-Flax/PLA	100	462 ± 6	13 ± 1	100	42 ± 3	143 ± 10	Failed
AP Flax/PLA ²	-	-	-	-	-	-	V-0
S-AP Flax/PLA ²	-	-	-	-	-	-	V-0

¹ The flame went out before reaching the timing mark after removal of the burner

² Sample did not ignite, thus burning rate could not be calculated

Table 4. Cone calorimetric results of control and FR flax/PP and flax/PLA composites from scoured and non-scoured fabric at 35 kW/m² external heat flux

Sample	TTI (s)	FOT (s)	Peak 1		Peak 2		THR (MJ/m ²)	EHC (MJ/kg)	Residue (%)
			PHRR (kW/m ²)	tPHRR (s)	PHRR (kW/m ²)	tPHRR (s)			
Flax/PP	28 ± 1	344 ± 11	429 ± 49	73 ± 6	372 ± 7	163 ± 1	89 ± 4	28 ± 1	3.9 ± 0.9
S-Flax/PP	26 ± 3	352 ± 11	477 ± 13	72 ± 0	400 ± 2	104 ± 6	92 ± 6	28 ± 1	4.3 ± 1.8
AP Flax/PP	28 ± 1	517 ± 6	255 ± 6	66 ± 0	199 ± 5	311 ± 7	81 ± 1	25 ± 0	13.3 ± 0.9
S-AP Flax/PP	27 ± 1	516 ± 16	254 ± 4	65 ± 4	208 ± 10	312 ± 28	83 ± 2	26 ± 0	14.6 ± 1.9
Flax/PLA	45 ± 2	232 ± 4	266 ± 34	69 ± 7	287 ± 10	142 ± 3	48 ± 3	14 ± 1	4.1 ± 1.0
S-Flax/PLA	49 ± 4	264 ± 12	267 ± 20	67 ± 4	270 ± 35	142 ± 3	54 ± 2	15 ± 0	3.7 ± 2.5
AP Flax/PLA	62 ± 1	81 ± 3	51 ± 6	73 ± 1	58 ± 17	299 ± 41	14 ± 4	4 ± 1	14.2 ± 0.5
S-AP Flax/PLA	57 ± 1	284 ± 8	66 ± 6	107 ± 30	73 ± 13	231 ± 18	23 ± 4	8 ± 1	14.6 ± 1.0

Table 5. Mechanical properties of scoured and flame retarded flax/PP and flax/PLA composites

Sample	Fibre Vol. Fraction (%)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Impact Modulus (GPa)
Flax/PP	37.5	6.6 ± 0.2	8.2 ± 0.5	11.0 ± 0.1
S-Flax/PP	37.5	8.4 ± 0.0	10.9 ± 1.4	11.4 ± 0.2
AP Flax/PP	37.5	5.7 ± 0.3	8.4 ± 0.6	9.4 ± 1.0
S-AP Flax/PP	37.5	6.2 ± 0.9	8.8 ± 1.8	9.5 ± 0.2
Flax/PLA	45.3	10.2 ± 1.4	16.2 ± 0.9	14.9 ± 0.2
S-Flax/PLA	45.3	10.9 ± 0.0	18.5 ± 1.4	15.4 ± 0.1
AP Flax/PLA	45.3	4.1 ± 1.5	4.7 ± 0.8	1.6 ± 0.2
S-AP Flax/PLA	45.3	4.5 ± 0.9	5.3 ± 3.3	1.9 ± 0.8